

CUTTING-EDGE HYBRID DEEP TRANSFER LEARNING APPROACH FOR POTATO LEAF DISEASE CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT. Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) stands as one of the most widely consumed vegetable items globally. Within the Indian market, it holds substantial commercial value and has emerged as the fourth most important food crop in the country, following rice. Ensuring a robust food security system becomes crucial for fostering prosperous potato production, given its significant contribution as a source of carbohydrates and potassium. However, the progress of agricultural development associated with potato production faces impediments from various diseases that undermine its growth. Monitoring plant diseases manually proves to be a challenging task due to the complex nature and time-consuming process involved. To address this issue, we have utilized deep transfer learning-based computational models that can detect leaf diseases at early stages. In this study, we have combined ResNet101, a deep transfer learning-based Convolution Neural Network (CNN) model, with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to effectively classify potato leaf diseases. To enhance the contrast of potato leaf images, we have applied the Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) method before feeding the images into the model. Through this approach, our architecture has achieved an impressive accuracy of 95.13% in identifying potato leaf diseases.

Keywords: *Potato, Leaf diseases, Transfer learning, PCA, Detection.*

INTRODUCTION

As per the 2021 report titled "Leveraging Digital Technology for Sustainable Agriculture" by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), it is emphasized that in order to sustainably feed a projected population of 9.7 billion by the coming years, global food production must be increased by 98 percent. To meet this target, it is crucial to effectively utilize available resources [1, 5]. Precision agriculture, in its current state, aims to establish a decision support system for farm management that optimizes output while concurrently preserving the resources employed. Potato stands as a highly successful and widely harvested vegetable worldwide. It is predominantly cultivated during the months of October to March, making it a winter season crop. In India, potato ranks as the fourth most significant crop, following rice and wheat, contributing significantly to economic growth. [2]. It has been documented that potato is consumed by over one billion individuals globally. Serving as both a high-quality vegetable and a staple food crop, it finds usage in the preparation of more than 100 diverse recipes in India. The nutritive value constituents per 100 gms of potato are given in Table 1.

Table 1. *Nutritive value constituents per 100 gms of potato.*

Constituents	Weight (grams)
Water	74.70
Carbohydrates	22.60
Proteins	1.60
Fibre	0.40
Fat	0.10
Minerals	0.60

Statistical data reveals that small farmers are responsible for generating over 80% of the agricultural output. However, they suffer significant crop losses of approximately 40-50% due to diseases and pests. Potatoes have significant commercial value in the Indian market, leading to extensive production alongside other vegetables. Unfortunately, potato crops are prone to diseases, and the prevailing climatic conditions contribute to the prevalence of these ailments at every stage of growth. It has been observed that disease-affected plants account for 20-30% of total crop loss [5]. Early identification of such conditions in plants is crucial to prevent substantial losses in yield and the overall agricultural output. Manual monitoring of plant diseases is very challenging and a time-consuming process. Therefore, there is a pressing need to minimize manual effort while ensuring accurate predictions and providing hassle-free solutions for farmers [7, 4]. To address this, researchers have employed advanced technologies such as computer vision, image processing, machine learning, and deep neural network architectures. These cutting-edge approaches aim to streamline the process and enhance the efficiency of disease identification in potato plants [5, 6].

This research aims to precisely detect early-stage potato leaf diseases and enhance farmers' awareness of these particular ailments. Utilizing the capabilities of computer vision, a subset of AI enabling machines to visually perceive using camera and computer technologies, this study strives to empower AI systems with advanced automation features. The primary emphasis of this inquiry is to create an optimal solution for the efficient identification of diseases in potato plant leaves. Various fields extensively utilize traditional machine learning algorithms or models. However, a major obstacle in their application is the challenging task of feature engineering. Fortunately, the advent of deep neural networks has opened new avenues, offering promising outcomes in plant pathology without the need for laborious feature engineering. Leveraging deep neural networks has led to remarkable advancements in image classification accuracy.

Adhikari *et al.* [4] employed CNN-based classifiers and conducted tests on a subset of images specifically related to tomato plant leaf diseases. The dataset used in their study comprised 113 samples of Gray spot, 121 samples of Late Blight, 111 samples of Bacterial Canker, along with healthy tomato leaf images that were included as well. The integration of image processing technology and classification algorithms facilitates improved detection and classification of plant leaf diseases. In another study [6], a deep CNN framework was employed to differentiate between healthy and unhealthy leaves. The authors demonstrated effective discrimination between the two leaf conditions. Furthermore, in [7], a novel technique was developed for leaf disease identification by leveraging the depth wise separable convolutional layer in MobileNet [8] and Reduced MobileNet. This innovative approach yielded promising results in the accurate

identification of leaf diseases. In [9], researchers employed a hybrid technique that combines autoencoders to detect leaf diseases. The model was trained using the PlantVillage dataset [10]. Several deep learning frameworks, namely AlexNet [11], VGG [12], AlexNetOWTbn [13], Overfeat [14], and GoogLeNet [15], were explored to detect normal or abnormal plants from leaf images [11]. In their study, the authors utilized a transfer learning-based approach to identify and detect diseases in specific regions of multiple crops, considering the PlantVillage dataset. The detection of early blight, late blight diseases, and healthy plants was accomplished using a deep learning approach in [16]. Similarly, in [17], authors utilized a CNN model to identify early blight, late blight diseases, and healthy classes. The identification of early blight, late blight diseases, and healthy leaves was addressed using various techniques, such as a Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) [18], a self-built CNN (SBCNN) [19], VGG19, multiple classifiers [20], and a multi-SVM-based framework [21]. There is a need for further enhancement of all the aforementioned methods to improve their performance in terms of accuracy.

In this paper, we have proposed a novel technique and architecture for classifying potato leaf diseases. The approach involves extracting image features using the ResNet101 deep transfer learning model and subsequently reducing the dimensionality of these features through the application of Principal Component Analysis (PCA). It is worthy to mention that before extracting the image features, all the images are passed through a contrast enhancement mechanism. By combining these methodologies, we aim to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of potato leaf disease detection in order to support farmers in making informed decisions [5]. PCA, is a powerful approach used to reduce the dimensionality of data by identifying a set of orthogonal axes known as principal components. These components effectively capture the highest amount of variance present in the dataset. They are derived from linear combinations of the original variables and are arranged in a descending order of significance. Importantly, the collective variance encompassed by all the principal components is equal to the overall variance in the original dataset. Thus, by using the PCA with ResNet101, the model has outperformed and achieved 95.13% classification accuracy.

The structure of the rest of the article is outlined below. In Section 2, demonstrates the materials and methods with proposed approach. In Section 3, we have presented the experimental results, then Section 4 covers the conclusions and future work for this research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dataset in used

A collection of potato disease images was sourced from the Kaggle dataset [3]. From this dataset, a total of 1800 images were randomly selected. Employing augmentation techniques, the image count increased to a total of 2152 images. The dataset consisted of three distinct disease classes. Specifically, two types of potato leaves, Early Blight and Late Blight, were infected, while the third class represented healthy, resistant leaves. Reference photos and corresponding disease names were utilized to accurately identify and label the images, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Samples of the potato leaf dataset.

Methods in used

This section provides an elaboration of the methodology pipeline employed in this research. The pipeline consists of three phases. In the first phase, data collection and data pre-processing are carried out. In the second phase, a deep ResNet101 model is applied to extract multiple features from the input images for model training. However, due to the high dimensionality of these features, PCA is employed to reduce their dimension. Finally, in the third phase, the classification task is performed using a fully connected layer.

The accuracy of a deep CNN model is highly reliant on the quality of the dataset used for training. To ensure robust performance, a data cleaning process is implemented after collecting the data. This process involves removing any faulty images identified in the dataset. Additionally, the images are resized to a fixed size of 224×224 . This resizing not only reduces the computational load during training but also contributes to achieving optimal results.

In the very beginning of the process, we have applied the Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) method to improve the contrast of the potato leaf images. Enhancing an image's contrast serves two primary objectives: (i) improving its visual appearance for better interpretation, and (ii) facilitating and increasing the performance of subsequent tasks. In Figure 2 (a-d) one sample result on potato leaf image after applying the CLAHE method is shown. The histograms of the image before applying CLAHE and after CLAHE is shown Figure 2(a-b).

Fig. 2. (a) Histogram before CLAHE (b) Histogram after CLAHE (c) without CLAHE (d) After CLAHE.

After the contrast image enhancement process, data augmentation process is applied. The data augmentation process is frequently utilized to enhance the diversity of images within a dataset by applying techniques such as image manipulation or the synthetic creation of new data. In this research, common manipulation techniques employed in the data augmentation process include image transformation through flipping, rotation, and translation. These techniques contribute to the increased diversity and variability of the dataset. Then one-hot encoding technique is applied for labeling the images. The array of images is then transformed into a NumPy array for quicker computation. Figure 3 illustrates the overall block diagram and architecture for the classification of potato leaf diseases using a deep transfer learning-based model. The term "ResNet" represents Residual Network, which encompasses multiple variants with varying numbers of layers (e.g., 18 layers, 34 layers, 50 layers, 101 layers, 152 layers). ResNet101 specifically refers to the variant that operates with 101 neural network layers [24].

In deep learning, a common challenge known as the vanishing/exploding gradient arises, wherein the gradient either becomes too small or excessively large. Consequently, increasing the number of layers leads to higher training and test error rates. Through analysis, the authors of this study identified the vanishing/exploding gradient as the cause of such errors. To address this issue, a Residual Network is employed, which incorporates skip connections. These connections allow for bypassing training in certain layers and directly connecting to the output. By adopting this approach, the network can learn the residual mapping instead of focusing solely on learning individual layers, thereby mitigating the vanishing/exploding gradient problem. The ResNet101 deep learning algorithm automatically extracts plant image features layer-by-layer, yielding high-level features prior to the fully connected (FC) layers. Typically, the last layer of deep learning networks such as ResNet101 employs SoftMax classification for output class prediction. Since the dimensionality of the extracted

features is often high, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is applied to reduce or transform these features [5].

(a)

```
In [19]: model = Sequential()
inputs = Input(shape=(n_PCA_components,)) #Shape = n_components
hidden = Dense(256, activation='relu')(inputs)
output = Dense(3, activation='softmax')(hidden)
model = Model(inputs=inputs, outputs=output)
print(model.summary())
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
Input_2 (InputLayer)	[(None, 1500)]	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 256)	384256
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 3)	771

Total params: 385,027
 Trainable params: 385,027
 Non-trainable params: 0

(b)

Fig. 3. (a) ResNet101 model with PCA. (b) Sample Code with fully connected layer with softmax.

PCA utilizes orthogonal transformations to identify correlated variables and transform them into uncorrelated ones. In order to achieve efficient classification, PCA is employed to reduce the dimensionality of the feature vector. Figure-4 demonstrates that by utilizing the first 1500 components, over and above 95% of the variability in the original image data can be captured. This retention of quality in the original images is deemed sufficient. Therefore, we have chosen to select and apply PCA with the aforementioned 1500 components. In Figure 3(b), sample of model preparation codes

are shown. It can be seen 1500 feature components are passed as input parameters to the fully connected layer model

Fig. 4. PCA analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the methodology discussion, this section will provide a detailed account of the experimental procedures, as well as the findings obtained from this study.

Experimental Setup

Various models were employed alongside the proposed model to conduct a comparative analysis of the evaluation measures. Programs are simulated in a machine with Processor: Xenon(R) CPU- E5-1630, 3.70 GHz clock speed and random-access memory of 32 GB having Windows 10 environment. All the methods and functions are implemented in Jupyter with Python 3.9 environment [24].

Evaluation metrics

Four different classification validity measures [24] such as (i) accuracy, (ii) precision, (iii) recall and (iv) F-score measure are used. In Table 2, details are given, where TP = True positive, TN = True negative, FN= False negative and FP=false positive.

Table 2. Evaluation measures with formula.

Measure	Formula
Accuracy	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + FP + TN}$
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
F-score	$\frac{2 * (Precision * Recall)}{(Precision + Recall)}$

Comparison of results and discussions

Within the literature, numerous existing methods are available for comparison. However, it is beyond the scope of this paper to compare the proposed model with all of these existing methods. Instead, in this work, the proposed model is compared to three other existing transfer learning-based models: VGG-16, ResNet-50, and Inception-50. Also, comparison is performed with Sholihati *et al.* [22], Singh and Kaur *et al.* [23]. These models were selected based on their popularity and their representation of the latest state-of-the-art work.

Fig. 5. At 4th layer, Heatmap visualization of ResNet101 model.

How in each layer feature map are generated to learn the image features it can be visualized in Figure 5. The internal views of the deep ResNet101 CNN model one sample of the Heatmap representation on one input potato leaf image is shown in Figure 5.

The proposed architecture i.e., ResNet101-PCA with CLAHE has able to achieved highest accuracy. In Figure 6, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves by using One-vs-Rest scheme for the proposed architecture is shown. This scheme compares each class against all the others. Normally, ROC curves are used in binary classification, where the true positive rate (TPR) and false positive rate (FPR) can be defined unambiguously. In our study, we are dealing with multiclass classification, thus a notion of TPR or FPR is obtained only after binarizing the output. In Figure 7, the confusion matrix achieved by ResNet101-PCA is shown. In Figure 7, out of the 431

testing image samples (20% of the dataset), the proposed architecture (ResNet101-PCA) misclassified 21 images.

The summary of the experimental results acquired by the different models is presented in Figure 8 (bar plots), where the performance is evaluated based on four validity measures: percentage accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. It can be observed in the figure that transfer learning-based models with PCA combination such as VGG-16, Inception-50, then Sholihati *et al.* [22], Singh and Kaur *et. al* [23] have attained lower values than the ResNet101-PCA. With the amalgamation of CLAHE contrast enhancement technique, PCA with the ResNet101 model has achieved higher accuracy.

Fig. 6. ROC-AUC for three different classes of CLAHE-ResNet101-PCA model.

In Table 3, ResNet101-PCA model with CLAHE is compared with two other well-known methods namely Sholihati *et al.* [22] and Singh and Kaur *et. al* [23] by considering various parameters. All the methods are applied on the same dataset. It can be observed that ResNet101-PCA has outperformed than others.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix generated by CLAHE-ResNet101-PCA model.

Table 3. Comparison of ResNet101-PCA model with two other models.

Contributors	Segmentation	Augmentation	Contrast enhancement	Accuracy
Sholihati et al. [22]	N/A	Yes	No	91.02%
Singh and Kaur et. al [23]	K-means	Yes	No	90.17%
Proposed ResNet101-PCA	N/A	Yes	Yes (CLAHE)	95.13%

Fig. 8. Comparison of different models with various measures.

CONCLUSION

Manual monitoring of plant diseases is a very challenging task and at the same time it is a time-consuming process. This article addresses this issue by proposing a deep neural network model that combines ResNet101 with PCA to effectively detect and classify potato plant leaf diseases into predefined categories. Before extraction of features, CLAHE contrast enhancement technique is also applied to the images. The ResNet101 model extracts a large number of features, leading to increased computational complexity. To mitigate this, PCA is employed to reduce the dimensionality, resulting in the selection of 1500 components. By judiciously integrating these techniques, we aim to provide an efficient solution for plant disease detection and classification. The proposed scheme has achieved an impressive accuracy of 95.13% in identifying potato leaf diseases. In the future, our plan is to expand the model's scope to include abiotic diseases resulting from nutrient deficiencies in crop leaves. Also, we are planning to incorporate the model into mobile or hand-held devices for live detection of diseases in crop fields. Moreover, our long-term objective involves extensive data collection on various plant diseases to enhance the model's capabilities.

Conflict of interest: There is no conflict of interest to this work.

Availability of Data: Data are collected from Kaggle data repository.

Author's Contributions: **Rubul Kumar Bania:** Carried out overall idea, implementation, experiments and analysis, drafting of the manuscript. **Nur Alom Talukdar:** Involve in implementation and drafting the manuscript. **Dibya Jyoti Bora:** Involve in data collection, revision, implementation.

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